

ANALYSIS OF CRIMINAL AND LEGAL PROBLEMS RELATED TO THE ILLEGAL USE OF DRONES

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Abstract: The development of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) technology plays an important role in crime prevention and detection. UAVs are used to investigate crimes, conduct investigations, and ensure public safety. In modern society, UAVs are applied in various fields, including security, environmental law enforcement, and the fight against terrorism. The regulation of UAVs' legal status and control over their legal and illegal use is a critical issue. In Uzbekistan, the use of UAVs is growing, but there are also legal issues related to the unlawful use of this technology. The use of UAVs, particularly micro-drones, raises new problems, such as committing crimes with their help. Therefore, it is necessary to clarify the legal framework for UAV use, improve their regulation, and develop new regulatory mechanisms to enhance the effectiveness of crime prevention.

Keywords: unmanned aerial vehicles, crime, legal regulation, security, digital technologies, drones, civil and commercial purposes, bribery, mobile phones, drugs.

The development of criminal law is inextricably linked with the development of modern technologies and sciences (anthropology, medicine, biology, chemistry, physics). Modern criminal methods and technologies used by criminals must respond to new challenges in society. One of such innovative technologies is unmanned aerial vehicles.

It should be noted that along with the development of technologies, drones have become widely used in various fields. They have become an important tool in a number of areas to increase accuracy and efficiency, ensure security, and save human life. The positive aspects of the use of drones are also growing in Uzbekistan. From agriculture to natural disasters and inspection of facilities, drones play an important role not only in increasing production efficiency, but also in ensuring public safety. This thesis examines the positive effects of drones, their beneficial opportunities in strengthening the economy, environment, and public safety. Drones, with their accuracy, speed and high technological capabilities, are an important factor in the development process of Uzbekistan, gaining social and economic significance.

Scholars have emphasized various aspects of criminal and legal issues related to the illegal use of drones. In particular, according to the results of a study conducted by Richard Rose and Caryn Peiffer, one third of the world's population regularly pays bribes to use public services, and in this process, there are cases of using drones as bribes. New trends associated with drones in modern crime reflect multifaceted factors and problems [1, p. 108]. It is necessary to understand the models of application of such technologies and develop recommendations for them, and to regulate them legally, since these situations soon give rise to scientific tasks that require practical solutions.

In modern scientific literature, the use of drones is of great importance in various fields. Scientists from China, Japan, the USA, Great Britain, the European Union and Russia are advancing the latest developments in this area [2, p. 787]. The most important issue is the study of legal issues related to digital technologies, especially drones (unmanned aerial vehicles), criminal-legal relations.

Modern technologies, including unmanned aerial vehicles, play an important role in crime and its prevention. The widespread use of unmanned aerial vehicles for civil and commercial purposes, along with increasing their technological capabilities, has also raised legal and ethical issues. As Bart Custers has noted, the technology of unmanned aerial vehicles already exists and is developing rapidly, but in parallel with this, ethical and legal questions are also arising, for example, how to use this technology and what restrictions should be imposed.

H.H. Perritt and E.O. Sprague argue that civilian use of drones is beneficial, but they can also pose risks and threats, including problems with law enforcement and infrastructure protection. It is clear that the penetration of drones into many areas is changing the technological and economic environment in society, but the question of how to implement laws to ensure their safety remains open [3, p. 400].

K.B. Sandvik argues that the use of military technology for civilian purposes (the militarization of security) is complicated. They observe that this situation has led to a violation of the rule of law and the emergence of public order drones. There is debate about the problematic aspects of arming the police with drones, as well as the long-term impact of this technology on operations [4, pp. 45-66].

The development of drone technology is giving rise to new forms of crime, which poses serious challenges for their legal regulation. Studies by M. Donatti

and other scientists have focused on the use of drones to commit crimes and the radio frequencies needed to prevent them. For example, drones have been used by some criminals to smuggle mobile phones and drugs into prisons [5, p. 299]. These cases demonstrate the dangerous use of drones and, at the same time, raise questions about their legal regulation. It can be argued that the use of drones poses new contemporary challenges in addressing issues of crime, terrorism, extremism, and privacy. The positive and negative aspects of technological development, the problems of legal regulation and the convergence of international and national approaches to them demonstrate the need to improve legislation to help ensure crime and public safety. To do this, it is necessary to develop clear rules on drones and the legal norms for their use, and to fully and safely regulate their operation.

In conclusion, the problems associated with drones, their activities and legal regulation are becoming increasingly complex. To do this, it is necessary to develop new laws and regulatory methods, as well as a full assessment of the ethical and legal aspects of the use of drones. In order for the use of drones to be effective in detecting and investigating crimes, their legal basis and legislative framework must be improved.

Thus, drones and their role in crime and post-crime activities are a global problem, which requires not only legislative foundations, but also their correct and active application. In Uzbekistan, the issue of using these devices has not yet been systematically regulated, which limits the possibilities for detecting and investigating crimes.

Studies show the importance of popularizing not only legal mechanisms, but also experience and developments to ensure the increased use of these technologies in connection with crime and law enforcement. Systematization, study and practical application of international and domestic approaches to regulation and legal mechanisms are necessary to improve the processes of studying and practical application, to increase the effectiveness of drones in detecting and investigating crimes.

It should be emphasized that the use of drones in crime requires the development of new laws and regulatory mechanisms to adequately address legal and ethical issues. Comprehensive legal regulation of the use of these technologies will not only help the country's economy, but will also have a positive impact on the role of such tools in detecting and investigating crime and post-crime activities

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